

PRIMERS AND QPCR DETAILS

The *dsrB* gene qPCR assay was based on the primer variant mixtures *dsrB*-F1a-h and *dsrB*-RSI1a-f (Lever et al. 2013) (all 5'-3'): *dsrB* F1a: CAC ACC CAG GGC TGG, *dsrB* F1b: CAT ACT CAG GGC TGG, *dsrB* F1c: CAT ACC CAG GGC TGG, *dsrB* F1d: CAC ACT CAA GGT TGG, *dsrB* F1e: CAC ACA CAG GGA TGG, *dsrB* F1f: CAC ACG CAG GGA TGG, *dsrB* F1g: CAC ACG CAG GGG TGG, *dsrB* F1h: CAT ACG CAA GGT TGG, *dsrB* 4RSI1a: CAG TTA CCG CAG TAC AT, *dsrB* 4RSI1b: CAG TTA CCG CAG AAC AT, *dsrB* 4RSI1c: CAG TTG CCG CAG TAC AT, *dsrB* 4RSI1d: CAG TTT CCG CAG TAC AT, *dsrB* 4RSI1e: CAG TTG CCG CAG AAC AT, *dsrB* 4RSI1f: CAG TTT CCA CAG AAC AT.

The bacterial 16S rRNA gene qPCR assay was based on the primer pair Bac908F 5'-AAC TCA AAK GAA TTG ACG GG-3' (modified from Ohkuma & Kudo 1998) and Bac1075R 5'-CAC GAG CTG ACG ACA RCC-3' (Ohkuma & Kudo 1998). The archaeal 16S rRNA gene qPCR assay was based on the primer pair Arch915Fmod 5'-AAT TGG CGG GGG AGC AC-3' (Cadillo-Quiroz et al. 2006) and Arch1059R 5'-GCC ATG CAC CWC CTC T-3' (Yu et al. 2005).

REFERENCES

Cadillo-Quiroz H, Bräuer S, Yashiro E, Sun C, Yavitt J, Zinder S. 2006. Vertical profiles of methanogenesis and methanogens in two contrasting acidic peatlands in central New York State, USA. *Environ Microbiol.* 8:1428-1440

Lever MA, Rouxel O, Alt JC, Shimizu N, Ono S, Coggon RM, Shanks WC, Lapham L, Elvert M, Prieto-Mollar X, Hinrichs K-U, Inagaki F, Teske A. 2013. Evidence for microbial carbon and sulfur cycling in deeply buried ridge flank basalt. *Science* 339:1305–1308. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1229240>.

Ohkuma M, Kudo T. 1998. Phylogenetic analysis of the symbiotic intestinal microflora of the termite *Cryptotermes domesticus* *FEMS Microbiology Letters* 164: 389–395.

Yu Y, Lee C, Kim J, Hwang S. 2005. Group-specific primer and probe sets to detect methanogenic communities using quantitative real-time polymerase chain reaction. *Biotechnol Bioeng.* 89:670-679.

Suppl. Figure S1: Sampling sites plotted with the free software Ocean Data View

(<https://odv.awi.de/>). Sites can also be seen directly on Google map

<https://drive.google.com/open?id=1rYE3drQ6eSkWIjRFQtpxwL265bM&usp=sharing>

Suppl. Figure S2: Relationship between age before present (BP) and depth of the studied sites. From left to right (A to E), the youngest sediment cores to the oldest. Note the difference in the age and depth scale between the different plots, which are visible with dashed lines reported from the precedent plot (D and E). Note also that the age based on sedimentation rates (Little Belt and Gr. Glacier Fjord) were recalculated into years before present (BP).

Suppl. Figure S3: Age model of the South Azores core. A) Ca/Fe ratios derived from XRF core scanning matched to the global $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ stack of benthic foraminifera isotope LR04 (Liesicki and Raymo, 2005, A Pliocene-Pleistocene stack of 57 globally distributed benthic ^{18}O records, *Paleoceanography*, 20, PA1003, doi:10.1029/2004PA001071)). The Marine Isotope Stages (MIS's) are indicated on the plot based on the corresponding $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ peaks. The odd numbers are associated to warmer interglacial periods. B) Depth-age model based on the ages of the MIS's.

Suppl. Figure S4: Parameter plots used to calculate mineralized C:N ratios. A linear regression was done between DIC and NH_4^+ ; $b[1]$ is the slope of the fit and $b[0]$ the intercept of the fit. Additional sites from expedition SKA-14 (Skagerrak, Baltic Sea) were added to increase the number of sites. We used only non-carbonated sediments to determine the DIC: NH_4^+ ratio. At the bottom of the figure, the table provides the diffusion coefficients corrected for temperature and salinity involved in the determination of the mineralized C:N (see methods). The median C:N ratio was 7.6, and this value was used to convert ammonium production rates into carbon oxidation rates.

Suppl. Table S1: Data input radiocarbon age (^{14}C) with modelled and calibrated age. Data from the Iceland basin have previously been published in (Van Nieuwenhove et al., 2018). Data from the Greenlandic fjords have previously been published in (Pelikan et al., 2019).

Site	core name	Labcode samples	Depth (average) cmbfsf	14C Age	Error	Unmodelled (BP)		Unmodelled (BP)		μ	σ	Mean Modelled Age (yr cal. BP)	Error
						1 sigma range		2 sigma range					
						from	to	from	to				
Faroe Bank (GC03)	Da-12-2-GC03	AAR-21487	10.5	7235	45	7751	7645	7806	7597	7699	53	7680	50
		AAR-21488	105.5	15850	60	18782	18645	18840	18569	18709	68	18647	69
		AAR-21489	130.5	16780	75	19880	19633	20000	19550	19769	118	19787	107
		AAR-21491	210.5	20090	110	23871	23562	24021	23406	23712	156	23771	138
		AAR-21493	275.5	23480	150	27525	27256	27646	27105	27380	137	27456	122
		AAR-21494	380.5	31400	350	35270	34575	35676	34247	34953	355	35426	340
		AAR-21495	430.5	35850	600	40748	39386	41339	38803	40074	654	40474	484
		AAR-21496	475.5	45200	1900	49611	46826	...	45602	47836	1281	45486	721
		AAR-21492 (outlier)	255.5	23100	140	27265	26847	27370	26604	27014	202		
AAR-21490 (outlier)	180.5	20240	100	24020	23730	24154	23580	23871	144				
Iceland Basin (GC01)	Da-12-11-GC01	AAR_17560	21.5	598	25	288	150	295	142	235	43	273	27
		AAR_23190	45.5	1416	25	987	920	1038	905	963	35	946	30
		AAR-23191	85.5	2234	25	1879	1801	1920	1747	1837	40	1853	38
		AAR-23192	140.5	3819	26	3817	3719	3860	3675	3766	48	3739	46
		AAR_17561	188.5	4562	35	4828	4730	4845	4682	4775	44	4802	29
		AAR-24460	235	7080	35	7595	7517	7637	7482	7558	38	7567	37
		AAR-24461	280	8383	35	9025	8930	9097	8849	8974	58	8981	44
		AAR_17562	330.5	9114	30	9916	9764	10026	9692	9852	81	9910	72
		AAR-24462	370	9583	47	10537	10393	10583	10286	10451	74	10503	59
		AAR-24463	410	10484	42	11809	11474	11895	11360	11640	143	11573	129
Gr. Continental Shelf (20G)	SA13-ST3-20G	AAR2067	163.5	2362	25							2048	43
		AAR2068	346	6446	28							6940	49
		AAR2069	435	9033	39							9617	55
		AAR2070	514	9896	39							10921	79
Gr. Side Fjord (40G)	SA13-ST6-40G	AAR21687	50	1372	24							919	32
		AAR21690	173.5	2668	2							2362	43
		AAR21691	196	3356	30							3218	54
		AAR21692	260	4458	40							4647	75
Gr. Main Fjord (30G)	SA13-ST5-30G	AAR20956	539	815	25							457	26
		AAR20955 (outlier)	25	652	25								

Suppl. Table S2: Parameters used to calculate NH_4^+ production rates in PROFILE.

Parameters	Faroe Bank	Iceland Basin	Greenland Cont. Shelf	South Azores	Eastern Equ. Pacific	Bering Sea
Site	Da-12-2	Da-12-1	Sa-13-3	Da-14-1	Leg201-1226B	Leg323-U1342-B
Temperature (°C)	8	3	4	3.2	1.8 to 25.6	2 to 6
Depth at top of calculation domain (mbsf)	0.12	0.12	0.0125	0.95*	1.3	0.54
Depth at bottom of calculation domain (mbsf)	5.925	4.215	6.05	6.04	417.7	42.57
Max number of equally spaced zones in interpretation	12					
Type of boundary conditions (C= concentration)	Top: C, Bottom: C					
Top boundary condition (mol m ⁻³)	0.010435179	2.61E-02	1.50E-01	9.69E-04*	5.17E-02	2.20E-02
Bottom boundary condition (mol m ⁻³)	0.192823958	2.16E-01	3.09E+00	7.00E-02	1.65E-01	2.88E-01
Molecular diffusion coefficient in water (D ₀ , m ² s ⁻¹)	1.21E-09	1.02085E-09	1.06E-09	1.03E-09	modified # [†]	modified # [†]
Expression for sediment diffusivity (D _s , m ² s ⁻¹)	D _s = D ₀ / (1 + 3*(1 - φ))				D _s = D ₀ / (τ ₂)	D _s = D ₀ / (1 + 3*(1 - φ))
Concentration in water column (C ₀) (mmol L ⁻¹)	0					
Minimum for production/consumption rate (mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹)	0					
Maximum for production/consumption rate (mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹)	1.00E+20					
Maximum deviation (in %) when accepting a calculated minimum	0.001					
Level of significance in the F statistics	0.05					
Points excluded	4 (0.3225, 4.75, 5.125, 5.525mbsf)	1 (1.415mbsf)	0	Removed negative values	0	2 (0.11 and 0.30 mbsf)
Number of first zones proposed by PROFILE	none	2	7	none	6	4
Final number of zones	3	3	3	1	3	3
Corrected the number of zones proposed by PROFILE	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes

*#The molecular diffusion coefficient in Eastern Equatorial Pacific and Bering Sea was calculated according to the temperature gradient (Equations 8 and 9). * the upper boundary conditions were set at 0.95 mbsf in the South Azores as the NH_4^+ concentration were below the limit of quantification within the upper 0.95mbsf.*